

Sample 17a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0361
{Si}	58.1
{Al, Si}	11.1
{Fe}	6.5
{Ca}	4.3
{Al, Si, K}	3.7
{Si, Ca LoP}	1.9
{Si, Ca HiP}	1.6
{Na, Al, Si}	1.4
{Si, Fe}	1.2
{Mg, Ca}	1.1
{S, Ca}	1.0
{Al}	0.9
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.8
{Na, Si}	0.6
{Si, K}	0.6
{Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Mg, Si}	0.4
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Si, S, Ca}	0.4
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
{Cl}	0.3
{Al, S}	0.3
{Mg}	0.2
{Al, Ca}	0.2
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.2
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Cl}	0.1
{Ti}	0.1
{Mn}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Na, Al}	0.1
{Si, Cl}	0.1
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{S, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.6
Pellet	1.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	1.3
BOF converter slag slopping	0.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.2
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.3
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	11.7
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.3
Carbon rich - other	2.1
Cement or BOF converter	2.3
Cement	1.9
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.5
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.8
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	61.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	9.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.2
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	4.8
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	2.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	11.7
Site - carbon-rich other	0.3
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	2.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	2.3
Urban	3.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	61.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	9.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 17b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0286
	{Si}	61.6
	{Al, Si}	9.8
	{Fe}	5.1
	{Ca}	3.8
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.5
	{Al, Si, K}	2.0
	{Si, Ca HiP}	2.0
	{Si, Fe}	1.4
	{S, Ca}	1.2
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.1
	{Mg, Si}	0.7
	{Si, K}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.2
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Al}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{S}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.9
Pellet	2.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.4
BOF converter slag	0.7
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.6
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	14.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.3
Carbon rich - other	3.1
Cement or BOF converter	2.5
Cement	3.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.4
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	60.7
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.5
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	3.4
Site - ore / hot metal	0.4
Site - slag	2.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.7
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	14.0
Site - carbon-rich other	0.3
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	3.1
Urban; rarely site - slag	2.5
Urban	4.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	60.7
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.5
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	0.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 17c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0588
	{Si}	63.8
	{S, Ca}	7.5
	{Al, Si}	7.4
	{Ca}	5.4
	{Fe}	3.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.6
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.9
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{S}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Ti}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.6
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	1.2
BOF converter slag slopping	1.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	4.9
Desulph slag	0.5
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	10.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
Carbon rich - other	2.2
Cement or BOF converter	3.0
Cement	4.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	3.7
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	61.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.8
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	7.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	10.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	2.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	3.0
Urban	8.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	61.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.1
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels